

Research in Management and Humanities

DWIJM VOL 1 Issue 1 (2022), 111-135

Available online at www.dwijmh.org

Journal homepage: <http://www.dwijmh.org>

Examining the Effect of Organizational Trust on Individual Work Performance, Employee Treatment on Organizational Trust and Work Performance.

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 10 January 2022

Received in rev. form 12 March 2022

Accepted 16 March 2022

Keywords:

*Organizational trust,
employee treatment,
individual work
performance,
counterproductive
work behavior*

JEL Classification:

D23; O15

ABSTRACT

Organizational trust is multifaceted, so considering its different components may help understand, act on, and manage it across stakeholders. This study explored the effect of organizational trust on individual performance and employee treatment on organizational trust and individual work performance. Reviewed literature was provided to deepen the understanding of the concepts and to establish the theories of the study. Descriptive assessment and correlational research design were applied with the employees of the Divine Word College of Laoag (DWCL) as respondents. Data were gathered via validated research questionnaires where no correlation was found between organizational trust and task and contextual performance. However, a correlation between organizational trust and counterproductive work behavior existed, as well as with employee treatment and organizational trust. Moreover, the analysis of variance suggests a correlation between employee treatment and organizational trust. The findings further indicate that there was no correlation between employee treatment and performance on a task and contextual aspects. However, counterproductive work behavior showed a correlation with employee treatment.

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Introduction

In a working environment with close coordination, trust becomes an important issue. The organizational structure that depicts the level of coordination and interdependence requires trust among those who are required to work together. The issue of trust becomes so important when the workplace is composed of people coming from different cultural backgrounds (Pamela, et.al, 2000). In this working environment, all activities and other kinds of transactions can only be accomplished if there is mutual trust among the parties who are dependent on each other when they exercise their

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duties and responsibilities. Along with this concept, trust becomes a predictor of work performance (Fukuyama, 1995). The research concluded that trust is a contributing factor to job satisfaction and organizational effectiveness (Morley, Pamela & Cezaria, 1997, Pamela & Kathleen, 2000).

Congruently, the top management concern is trust-building at the organizational level. Trust itself is defined by Robbins (1999) as “the belief in the integrity, character, and ability of a leader”. Kreitner and Kinicki (1998) termed it as “reciprocal faith in one's intentions and behaviors.” Funk and Wagnalls (1985) referred to it as “a confidant reliance on the integrity, honesty, or justice of another.” Organizational trust can be defined at the individual level as “a psychological state comprising willingness to accept vulnerability based on positive expectations of an organization” (Fulmer & Gelfand, 2013). While Starness, et.al (2010) defined organizational trust in terms of intra-organizational trust which focuses on the employer-employee relationship. Others also define organizational trust as between workers and those who are managing the organization (Dirks & Ferrin, 2002).

The researcher has been working in the school institutions for the last 25 years and he has been occupying different positions in several institutions. From such an experience, the researcher has been witnessing performance problems on the part of employees. Issues can be identified such as absenteeism, leaving work during office hours, coming late to class, submitting the report late, and sleeping during office hours. The management has been trying to identify the reasons behind these startling issues but has not found a perfect solution to improve these kinds of behaviors. Motivating employees to perform is focused on financial reward, thereby neglecting other factors of the workplace environment. These include employee treatment (Abun, et.al. 2020), workplace well-being (Abun, et.al, 2021), workplace relationships (Abun, et.al, 2018), and organizational climate (Abun, et.al. 2021). This premise prompted the researcher to pursue this investigation that organizational trust affects employees' work performance.

The study will be divided into several parts. The first part is the introduction which explains the rationale of the study. This is followed by the literature review which reviews the existing concept and findings of the previous studies related to the current topic that can help strengthen the theory of the current investigation. The third part is the research methodology which discusses the research design, population of the study, the locale of the study, research procedures, data gathering instruments, and statistical instruments. The fourth part is the presentation of data and analysis of data. The final part is the result and discussion which explains further the implication of the study.

Literature Review

This part discusses the concept and theories of the previous studies and literature related to the current investigation. Therefore, a thematic discussion is presented.

The Concept of Organizational Trust

Trust affects organizational performance (Shaw, 1997). Unfortunately, the management does not seem to understand the great implication for the organization even though the trustworthiness of the organization is declined (Tyler & Kramer, 1996). It is a reality that organizations are involved in transactions with other organizations and even with their employees. Successful transactions depend on the trust of both parties, therefore, the existence of an organization depends on trust (Drucker, 1999). Thus, management needs to understand trust and its role in its effectiveness.

Online Merriam-Webster Dictionary defines trust as “assured reliance on the character, ability, strength, or truth of someone or something”. The emphasis of this definition is reliance and confidence. Someone relies on and believes in the truthfulness/ability of someone else or something. The object of trust is not just a human person but even something such as an organization. In line with this concept, Collins Dictionary defines trust as “reliance on and confidence in the truth, worth, reliability of a person or thing”. Cambridge Dictionary defines trust as “to believe that someone is good and honest and will not harm you, or that something is safe and reliable”. Thus, all these definitions emphasize the common elements of trust such as reliance, honesty, confidence, and belief in someone or something, that someone or something would not disappoint them or would not take advantage of him/them. All transactions rely on these aspects of trust and therefore the success of transactions or negotiations depends on trust (Drucker, 1999).

Although there is no common agreement on the definition of trust (Kurstedt, 2002), a certain definition of trust was established to set the direction of this paper. Cummings and Bromiley (1996) defined trust as "an individual belief or a common belief among a group of individuals that another individual or group makes a good faith effort to behave following any commitments both explicit or implicit, is honest in whatever negotiations preceded such commitments, and does not take advantage of another even when the opportunity is available". According to this definition, all transactions, negotiations, dialogues, and interactions rely on these elements to be successful which means that all parties must have good faith or must not have hidden agenda, be honest and dependable, and must not take advantage of the other. According to them someone or something is trustworthy if one possesses these elements. However, their definition seems to be lacking one element: the welfare of others. The definition was conceptualized last 1995 and Bromiley, through personal conversation with the current author, recognized definition lacked such element. Therefore, along with such concern, the definition of Shockley-Zalabak, et.al (2000) and Mishra (1996) can be added to the definition of trust based on this study. Shockley-Zalabak, et.al. (2000) define trust as a belief that "another individual, group or organization is competent, open and honest, concerned, reliable and identified with the common goals, norms, and values". Mishra (1996, p. 265) similarly explained trust as "one party's willingness to be vulnerable to another party based on the belief that the latter party is competent, open, concerned and reliable".

Cummings and Bromiley (1995), Shockley-Zalabak, et.al (2000), and Mishra (1996) referred to organizational trust as intra-organizational trust (Starness, et.al. 2010) which is described as the trust of workers toward their immediate superiors or trust between workers and those running the institution, between work units or between team member. In other words, organizational trust refers to interpersonal trust within workgroups or teams (Dirks, 1999, Meyers, et.al, 1995). Along with this concept, Solomon and Flores (2001) identified several characteristics of trust such as basic, simple, blind, and authentic trust. Basic trust refers to the capability of a person to talk or to meet another person comfortably without any suspicions and is willing to enter an intimate relationship even though he/she has no complete information about the person. Simple trust simply means that a person trusts another person without any suspicions, justification, or scrutiny because there is no reason to doubt or question the trustworthiness of the person. One naively believes the person to be good and trustworthy. Blind trust is defined as a trust of a person toward another person or organization that has been exposed to violation and betrayal, but the person refused to believe that it has happened and the person refuses to believe that the same thing could happen again in the future. Lastly, authentic trust, as Starness, et.al (2010) pointed "fully self-aware, cognizant of its conditions and limitations, open to new and even unimagined possibilities, based on choice and responsibility rather than the mechanical operations of predictability, reliance, and rigid rule-following. In this case, trusting another person can face the risk of trusting another person. The person believes that one is competent and is willing to back him/her up (Scholtes, 1988). As Meyer, et.al (1995) clarified the trustor is willing to trust the trustee based on the capacity of performing the task and willingness to do good for the trustor and having the right values.

This study adopted the definition of Cummings and Bromiley (1995) and Shockley-Zalabak, et.al (2000) because they conform to the theoretical and conceptual framework. The concern for the welfare of others is added to the definition of trust of Cummings and Bromiley (1995) because this is suggested by Bromiley in his email to the current researcher when he asked him to adopt their organizational trust inventory (OTI). Thus, the definition of Shockley-Zalabak, et.al. (2000) which includes the concern for others, is taken because it covers the concern for the welfare of others. Therefore, the definition of organizational trust that we adopt is "It is an individual belief or a common belief among a group of individuals that another individual or group makes a good faith effort to behave following any commitments both explicit or implicit, is honest in whatever negotiations preceded such commitments, is concerned with the welfare of others, and does not take advantage of another even when the opportunity is available". The study views trust as an intra-organizational trust. Ilter (1998) calls it institutional trust in the workplace which refers to the trust among the employees, and between employees and the management. Based on the definitions of trust, then trust is not a single-dimensional construct, but it is a multidimensional construct. Multidimensional construct means that trust has several dimensions, and these dimensions are related and treated as a single concept. These dimensions are cognitive, affective, and conative or behavioral dimension.

Organizational Trust is a Multidimensional Construct

It is a reality that an organization is composed of different individuals, different work units or groups, and teams. The success of an organization is depending on people and the cooperation among people and with the manager and different work units. The glue that ties the cooperation among people is not using coercion or deterrent measures as pointed out by Meyers, et.al (1995), but it is a trust that people have toward each other, toward the administrators/managers, and toward other units or teams that make the people are comfortable to work together. It is trust that makes people open toward each other, accepting criticism, and open discussion to improve the work (Edmondson, 1999). Thus, a working environment that is built on trust must be the priority concern of the management.

Trust is not only a matter of knowledge, but it is also a matter of feeling and behavior. Ozen (2003) opined that the root of trust is rationality or emotion. Based on such distinction, there are several dimensions of trust such as cognitive and affective trust (McAllister, 1995). Trust is considered cognitive when people trust someone else, something, a group, a team, or management based on his/her rational assessment. In other words, trust is based upon what he knows or believes about the person, something, a group, a team, or an organization. Based on his knowledge that the person, something, group, team, the organization is dependable (Ozen 2003). However, this kind of trust is not just a matter of one-day interaction but is based on the intensive interaction of the two parties. An intensive relationship between two parties' results in two things such as cognitive and affective trust. According to McAllister (1995), once the relationship is intensive, the relationship of trust gets stronger and deeper and those involved in the relationship make a mutual, emotional investment in their relationship. When emotions are involved in the relationship of trust, one is concerned with the welfare of the other party which is expressed through the act of kindness. Thus, cognitive, and affective trust are correlated because trust is originated from the knowledge of the person toward the other person, something, organization, group, or team which is the result of the experience of intensive interaction between the parties (McAllister, 1995). However, Cummings and Bromiley (1995) defined trust as belief, they included the behavioral aspect of trust. Hence, there are three dimensions of trust to be measured such as affective, cognitive, and intended behavior dimensions (cognitive dimension (Cummings & Bromiley, 1995 as cited from Creeds, Fabrigar & Petty, 1994).

Organizational Trust and Organizational Performance

Research on organizational trust and its influence on organizational performance is nothing new. This topic has drawn the attention of many researchers because of its significant influence on human life, human relations, human cooperation, and organization. There is an increase in awareness of the importance of trust (Cook, 2001). Organizations are finding ways to bring back the waning trust in human relations, and improve social cooperation and solidarity (Misztal, 1996, as cited in Mollering, et.al 2004; Seligman, 1997). Accordingly, Luhmann (1979) stated that trust is important for reducing social complexities. Thus, the continuous interest in investigating organizational trust is an indication that people come to realize its significance and perhaps propose solutions on how to restore trust among people and organizations (Mollering, et.al, 2004). Confucius (551-479 BC) considered the essence of trust in worthwhile social relations (Hann, 1968, cited by Mollering, et.al 2004). Early philosophers, sociologists, and political scientists have opined that trust is essential to prevent societal vulnerability from paralyzing social life. These are traced from the writings of Hobbes, Lock, and Hume (Dunn, 1988, Hollis, 1998). Goffman (1963) emphasized the significance of trust in social interactions and safeguarding social processes. Even Erikson (1965) found that trust is important in child development. In view of this, Giddens (1990) suggested that trust must be cultivated at the personal level to overcome the instability of society. Similarly, Zand (1972) clarified that trust is a process and a spiral. It is a spiral because trust leads to more trust and vice versa. Researchers, according to Mollering, et.al (2004), believed that trust will enable the manager to attain organizational openness and competitiveness while reducing social uncertainty and vulnerability.

The researchers further suggested continuing the discussion on trust in the institutions (Bachmann, 2001; Giddens, 1990; Lane and Bachmann, 1996) and conduct research along with individual trust and organizational trust. It is noteworthy, that as early as 1967, Rotter (1967) developed Interpersonal Trust Scale (ITS) to measure individual predisposition and the level of trust of people toward other actors, media, and institutions. Barber (1983) likewise, investigated societal trust toward political representatives and institutions. In the 1990s, however, trust research focused on the formulation of the concepts. Recently, this was expanded into empirical investigations (Mollering, et.al 2004).

There have been a lot of researchers on organizational trust and its effect on employees' performance, organizational performance, commitment, turnover intention, employees' job satisfaction, and work commitment. Take, for example, Onyeizugbe, et.al (2018) who conducted a study on organizational trust and employee performance. Their study concluded that it is positively correlated to employees' performance. This finding is strengthened by the study of Li, et.al (2018), Li, et.al (2007), Buenaventura-Vera, and Gudziol-Vidal (2020) on the effect of organizational trust on job performance. Their studies presented scientific evidence that organizational trust predicts individual performance. Organizational trust also affects organizational performance (Guinot, et.al, 2014, Niculescu, 2015). In terms of the effect of organizational trust on job commitment, studies have shown that it influences the work commitment of employees (Gider, et.al, 2019, Fard & Karimi, 2015). The same effect has been found related to job satisfaction. Many studies have demonstrated that organizational trust affects the job satisfaction and turnover of employees namely: Gucer and Demirdag (2014), Arter (2017), Kumar (2017), Recica and Dogan (2019), Pourkeiani, and Tanabandeh (2016), Varihanna, et.al (2020), Huda (2019).

In a nutshell, organizational trust is an important element to consider in management's function because it affects practically all aspects of the organization specifically performance, commitment, and employee satisfaction. Based on these researchers, one can conclude that organizational trust is the foundation of effective management. Subsequently, building organizational trust is a process (Zand, 1972) that can only be established with a relentless trusting working relationships.

Employee Treatment: Workers' Rights and Respect in the Workplace

Online Merriam-Webster Dictionary defines the word "treatment" as "the act or manner or an instance of treating someone or something: such as a: conduct or behavior towards another, b: the action or manner of dealing with something (such as a topic) often in a specified way". The definition emphasizes the right behavior on how to deal with others or something. In the same vein, the online Cambridge Dictionary also defines treatment as "the way you deal with or behave toward someone or something". The emphasis is still on the right conduct to deal with other people. Along with these definitions, Collins Dictionary defines treatment as "the way you behave towards them or deal with them".

In the school context, employee treatment means how the management or school administrators behave or deal with their employees (Abun, et.al, 2020). The Labor Code of the Philippines specifically, refers to employee treatment as to how employers address workers' rights. The management or the employer needs to protect workers' rights by following the labor laws of the Philippines. The Labor Code of the Philippines identified workers' rights such as security of tenure, self-organization, collective bargaining, just and human conditions of work, strike/concerted effort, participation in decision making, just share in the fruits of the production, living wage and CBA rights (Jimenez, n.d). These rights originated from the 1987 Constitution of the Republic of the Philippines article XIII on Human Rights and Social Justice (GOVPH, 1987).

Employee treatment may not be limited to protecting workers' rights as indicated in the Labor Code of the Philippines, but it also includes respect for employees in the workplace. The command to respect originated from the whole view of human beings. All human beings have intrinsic value in themselves (Regan, 2004) and other beings and therefore,

it is imperative for one human being to respect another human being and other beings. Such respect is not because the person is good to you but because of dignity. Respecting another person is a moral law (Liebling, 2011). On the contrary, Johnson, (2016) believes that it is about humanity. The principle of humanity enable them to engage in self-directed rational behavior in pursuit of a goal. This principle prohibits human beings to treat another one as means to other ends (Johnson, 2016). This is the basic moral principle of management that employees are not treated as means to their ends.

Individual Work Performance: A Multidimensional Construct.

The success of an organization depends on the work performance of employees. The management should monitor employees' work performance to determine measures of intervention in case of problems because ignoring the performance issue may cause problems for the organization (Combs, et.al. 2006). The key to ensuring organizational performance is individual performance, however, it is not just measured by one element such as productivity or quality output (Abun, et.al 2021) but it includes behavioral elements that may contribute to the high or low performance (Campbell, 1990). The management needs to understand what constitutes a performance because an individual performance cannot be measured from one dimension only, as done in past studies (Abun, et.al. 2021). Since it is a multidimensional construct, researchers have recognized their difficulty in measuring work performance ((Stewart & Walsh, 2009).

Many performance assessment studies focused on individual work performance related to productivity and quality of output which is used by Renn and Fedor (2001). Though measuring performance based on productivity, may measure certain elements, this performance measurement does not represent the individual work performance. This has been noted by Campbell (1990) and Griffin (1993) because it does not reflect the complexities of different work behaviors in work performance. Many studies measured performance based on many other indicators such as absenteeism, salary, and promotion (Motowidlo, et. al,1997). Though these elements (productivity, absenteeism, salary, and promotion) may measure performance to a certain extent, they may not measure the whole job performance. Measuring performance based on these elements does not reflect it. It is because performance refers to "the expected organizational value of behavior" (Motowidlo, et.al, 1997). Moreover, performance refers to behaviors that help not the organization in accomplishing its objectives. Since it refers to behavior, performance should be measured from different dimensions which may include task, contextual performance, and counterproductive behavior (Motowidlo, & Kell, 2012, Koopmans, et.al, 2014, Campbell, 1990, Griffin, et.al, 1993, Fay & SonSonntag010). Task performance is the capability to perform a task. Thus, it refers to the proficiency or competency that one has (Griffin, et.al., 2007, Wisecarver, 2007, Campbell, 1990, Rollins & Fruge, 1992) in carrying out duties and responsibilities. The second element or dimension of individual work performance is contextual performance. It refers to the behavior that helps create a positive work environment. Borman & Motowidlo, (1993) defined contextual performance as "a behavior that supports the organizational, social and psychological environment in which the technical core must function". Other researchers have called contextual performance an organizational citizenship behavior namely, Viswesvaran and Ones (2000), Rotundo and Sackett (2002), and Allen (2008). Organizational citizenship behavior means that employees are not only performing their tasks as demanded by their job description, but they are taking on extra work and extra time on their initiative to help the organization (Rotundo & sacket, 2002). The third element of individual performance is counterproductive behavior. This behavior is contrary to citizenship behavior. If organizational behavior helps an helpsorganization, counterproductive work behaviors not. They harm the orgorganization pmans, et.al. 2014). The behavior may include absenteeism, leaving early from work, doing other things within office hours, theft, or destroying the organization's assets (Abun, et.al. 2021). Other researchers call these kinds of behavior hazardous behavior (Murphy, 1989) which cause damage to the organization.

Conceptual Framework

Independent Variables

Dependent Variables

Source: Cummings and Bromiley (1995), Abun (2021), Koopmans, et.al (2014)

The conceptual framework reflects how the theories operate. It shows that organizational trust affects directly individual work performance. This can happen when there is the proper treatment of employees in terms of their rights and respect.

Statement of the Problems

The paper aims to examine the link between organizational trust, employee treatment, and performance. It seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the organizational trust of Divine Word Colleges in terms of:
 - a. cognitive trust and
 - b. affective trust?
2. What is the employee treatment of Divine Word Colleges in terms of:
 - a. worker's rights and
 - b. respect in the workplace?
3. What is the individual work performance of employees in terms of:
 - a. task performance.
 - b. contextual performance, and
 - c. counterproductive work behavior?
4. Is there a relationship between organizational trust and individual work performance?
5. Is there a relationship between employee treatment and organizational trust?
6. Is there a relationship between employee treatment and individual work performance?

Assumption

The study assumed that organizational trust affects the individual work performance of employees. It also assumed that the theory of the study is correct. Further, the tools to carry it out reflected its content and the questionnaires are valid.

Hypothesis

Researchers have found that organizational trust affects employees' job satisfaction and work commitment. Based on such theory, the current study hypothesized that organizational trust affects the individual work performance of employees as mediated by employee treatment.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The current study limited its investigation on the organizational trust of the employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region and delimits investigation of organizational trust on its affective and cognitive dimension, individual performance along with task performance, contextual performance, counterproductive behavior, and employee treatment along worker's right and respect in the workplace.

Research Methodology

An essential requirement for scientific research is the research methodology, therefore, this part presents the process of the study. The study was conducted using appropriate research methodologies such as research design, data gathering instruments, population, the locale of the study, data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

The nature of the study is quantitative research and it used descriptive assessment and correlational research design. Descriptive research describes the characteristics of the population or the phenomena. It focuses more on the “what” of the research subject rather than the “why” of the research subject” (Baht, 2020 para. 1). This research design ascertained the level of organizational trust and its effect on the individual work performance of employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region. Descriptive research pictured the profiles, frequency distribution, characteristics of people, situations, phenomena, or relationship variables. In short, it describes “what is” about the data (Ariola, 2006, cited by Abun, 2019).

Concerning the current study, the descriptive correlational method was deployed. It examined the level of organizational trust and its effect on the individual work performance of employees while employee treatment on organizational trust and individual work performance were also determined.

The Locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word College of Laoag and Divine Word College of Vigan. These two colleges are in two different provinces: Ilocos Sur and Ilocos Norte.

Population

All employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region were the respondents. The total enumeration sampling was used among the 250 employees.

Data Gathering instruments

The study adopted validated questionnaires of Cummings and Bromiley (1995) on organizational trust. The individual work performance questionnaires of Abun (2020) on employee treatment and that of Koopmans’, et.al (2014) were adopted.

Data Gathering Procedures

In the process of data gathering, the researcher sent letters to the president of the college, requesting them to allow the researcher to conduct the survey in the college. The researcher personally met the presidents and employees and requested them to answer the questionnaires.

The questionnaires were retrieved from the presidents’ representatives.

Statistical Treatment of Data

In congruence with the design of the study, descriptive and inferential statistics were used. The weighted mean determined the level of organizational trust, individual work performance, and employee treatment. Pearson r measured the correlation between organizational trust and individual performance, employee treatment and work

performance.

The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Interpretation
4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree/Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree/High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat Agree/Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree/Low
1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree/Very Low

Data Presentation and Analysis.

The results of the study were obtained through research questionnaires and statistical tools particularly weighted mean and analysis of variance was used to analyze the data. The presentation follows the statement of the problem of the study.

Problem 1. What is the organizational trust of Divine Word Colleges in terms of:

- a. Cognitive trust
- b. Affective trust

Table 1. The organizational trust of Divine Word College in terms of Cognitive Trust (n=160)

Indicators		Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
	Cognitive Trust		
1	We think the people in this institution tell the truth	3.51	A/H
2	We think the CEO (the President) of this institution meets its negotiated obligation to the employees	3.41	A/H
3	In our opinion, the CEO (the President) is reliable	3.40	SWA/M
4	We think that the people in this institution succeed by not stepping on other people	3.44	A/H
5	We think that our immediate heads are not taking advantage of their employees' weaknesses	3.42	A/H
6	We think that the heads do not mislead us	3.43	A/H
	Composite Mean	3.44	A/H

Source: Cummings and Bromiley (1995)

Legend:

<i>Range of Mean Values</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
4.21 - 5.00	Strongly Agree/Very high
3.41 - 4.20	Agree/High
2.61 - 3.40	Somewhat agree/Moderate
1.81 - 2.60	Disagree/Low
1.00 - 1.80	Strongly disagree/Very low

The cognitive trust obtained a composite mean of 3.44 which is considered “agree or high”. Several indicators are rated high, particularly concerning telling the truth, meeting its negotiated obligation to the employees, not stepping on other people, not taking advantage of employees' weaknesses, and not misleading employees. However, one indicator was rated moderate along with the reliability of the CEO. Cumming and Bromiley (1996) suggest that organizational trust has an important role in helping knowledge sharing among organizational members. As the level of trust increases, knowledge-sharing behavior improves. Gider, et al. (2019) argued that organizational trust affects employee commitment and job satisfaction.

Table 2: Organizational Trust in terms of Affective Trust

Indicators		Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
	Affective Trust		
1	We feel that the heads are fair to everyone	3.40	SWA
2	We feel that the CEO (the president negotiates with us honestly)	3.26	SAW
3	We feel that the heads keep their words	3.35	SWA
4	We feel that co-employees are honest	3.53	A
5	We feel that the heads keep their commitments	3.41	A
6	We feel that the heads do not take advantage of employees	3.36	SWA
	Composite Mean	3.38	SWA
Overall Mean	Cognitive Trust and Affective Trust	3.41	A

Source: Cummings and Bromiley (1995).

As gleaned from the data, the affective trust gained a composited mean rating of 3.41 which is also interpreted as "agree or high". Two indicators were rated high related to honesty, and keeping commitments. While there were four indicators rated moderate in terms of fair treatment, the CEO's honesty, keeping their word or promises, and not taking advantage of their employees. Research suggests that high trust elevates employees' morale and loyalty (Gucer & Demirdag, 2014). Other researchers also suggest that low trust can sabotage productivity, engagement, retention, organizational dysfunction, psychological safety, and decrease energy (Zak, 2017, Hungerford & Cleary, 2020, Brown, et al., 2015).

Problem 2: What is the employee treatment of Divine Word Colleges in terms of:

- a. *Worker's rights*
- b. *Respect in the workplace*

Table 3. Employee treatment of Divine Word College in terms of Worker's rights (n=160)

Indicators		Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
	Worker's right		
1	Security of tenure is followed	3.25	SWA
2	Employees feel secure when they are already employed	3.48	A
3	The offices are comfortable enough to work	3.13	SWA
4	Employees are allowed to participate in decision-making through their representative	3.20	SWA
5	Management listens to the ideas of employees through their representative	3.35	SWA
6	Salary is given according to rank and job grade	3.34	SWA
7	Salaries are beyond the minimum wage	3.35	SWA
8	Employees' problems are solved through due process	3.20	SWA
9	The employees' freedom of expression is protected	3.28	SWA
10	The employees are allowed to organize themselves	3.29	SWA
	Composite Mean	3.35	SWA

Source: Abun, et.al., (2020).

The worker's rights garnered a composite mean rating of 3.35 which is understood as "somewhat agree or moderate". This rating implies something has gone wrong. Of the 10 indicators included in the investigation, there is only one indicator rated high along with the security of tenure. While the nine indicators are rated at a moderate level related to the comfortable workplace, participation in decision making, listening to the ideas of employees, salaries given according to job grade and rank, salaries beyond minimum wage, following dues process in solving issues, freedom of expression, and self-organization. UN Human Rights International Convention (1990) ratified the adoption of protection of the rights of all migrant workers and members of their families. The ratification is motivated by the realities of workers' rights that have not been given attention by employers. The United Nations (2020) urges all

nations, public and private organizations to protect workers' rights and provide decent work because the UN found that more than 630 million workers around the globe did not earn enough to lift themselves and their families, around 7,500 each day workers die due to poor working condition, 74% of countries exclude workers from the right to establish and join a trade union and hundreds of millions of people suffer from discrimination.

Table 4: Employee Treatment in terms of Respect in the Workplace

Indicators		Weighted mean	Descriptive Interpretation
	Respect in the Workplace		
1	I feel valued in my institution	3.43	A
2	All employees have equal access to professional development and training opportunities.	3.36	SWA
3	The management treats employees with respect.	3.40	SWA
4	The behavior of the management toward the employees is appropriate and does not make fun of employees	3.36	SWA
5	The management typically welcomes ideas from employees who have different views, opinions, and experiences than theirs	3.38	SWA
6	The management can work with employees coming from different backgrounds.	3.48	A
7	The management can openly discuss any concerns with the employees	3.31	SWA
8	Our employees are promoted based on their skills, abilities, and experience, regardless of gender, age, ethnicity, sexual orientation, or other unique characteristics	3.42	A
9	The management would forgive an honest mistake of employees	3.42	A
10	Overall, our institution is a respectful place to work	3.46	A
	Composite Mean	3.40	SWA
Overall Mean	Worker's Rights and Respect in the workplace	3.34	SWA

Source: Abun, et al. (2020).

Legend:

Range of Mean Values

4.21 - 5.00

3.41 - 4.20

2.61 - 3.40

1.81 - 2.60

1.00 - 1.80

Descriptive Interpretation

Strongly Agree/very high

Agree/high

Somewhat Agree/moderate

Disagree/low

Strongly disagree/very low

The table illustrates that respect in the workplace gained a composite mean of 3.34 which is considered "somewhat agree or moderate. Notably, the result specifies something to be done to improve respect in the workplace. From the ten indicators, there were five items or indicators included in the survey rated with high mean related to being valued by the institution, working together with employees from different backgrounds, promotion based on competence, the forgiveness of honest mistakes, and a respectful place to work. While the other five items were rated moderate in terms of equal access to professional development and training opportunities, treating employees with respect, appropriate behavior toward the employees, and open discussion with the employees on organizational issues. Clarke and Mahadi (2017) suggested that mutual respect in the workplace can affect the affective commitment and job satisfaction of the employee. ISMP (2014) also suggested that lack of respect in the workplace causes fear, anger, shame, confusion, uncertainty, isolation, self-doubt, depression, and physical ailments like insomnia, fatigue, nausea, and hypertension which consequently affect performance.

Problem 3. What is the individual work performance of employees in terms of:

- a. **Task performance**
- b. **Contextual performance**
- c. **Counterproductive work behavior**

Table 5. Individual work performance of employees in terms of Task Performance (n=160)

Indicators	Task Performance	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	I manage to plan my work so that it is done on time	4.05	A
2	My planning was optimal	3.88	A
3	I kept in mind the results that I have to achieve in my work	4.01	A
4	I can separate main issues from side issues at work	4.00	A
5	I know how to set the right priorities 1 2 3 4 5	4.08	A
6	I manage to finish my work so that it was done on time	3.94	A
	Composite Mean	3.99	A

Source: Koopmans, et al. (2014).

Gleaned from the data, the employee's task performance gained a composite mean rating of 3.99 which is considered "agree or high". Even if the items or indicators are taken singly, all items are rated within the same level of mean range with the interpretation of "agree or high" particularly related to the ability to manage the work and finish on time, optimal plan, keeping the result in mind to be achieved, separating main issues from side issues at work, setting the right priorities, and the ability to finish the work on time and as planned. A study suggests that people with high task performance tend to be more self-controlled, more responsible, and more persistent (Gao, et al., 2021) which consequently affects individual work performance (Whiting, et al., 2008).

Table 6: Individual Work Performance in terms of Contextual Performance (n=160).

Indicators	Contextual Performance	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	I took on extra responsibilities	4.01	A
2	I started a new task myself when my old ones were finished	3.96	A
3	I took on a challenging work task, when available	3.98	A
4	I worked at keeping my job knowledge up-to-date	4.00	A
5	I worked at keeping my job skills up-to-date	4.00	A
6	I came up with creative solutions to new problems	3.92	A
7	I kept looking for new challenges in my job	3.98	A
8	I did more than was expected of me	3.94	A
9	I actively participated in work meetings	3.88	A
10	I actively look for ways to improve my performance at work	4.05	A
11	I grasped opportunities when they presented themselves	4.00	A
12	I knew how to solve difficult situations and setbacks quickly	3.96	A
	Composite mean	3.97	A

Source: Koopmans, et al. (2014).

The table reveals that the contextual performance garnered a composite mean rating of 3.97 which is interpreted as "agree or high". Interestingly, even when the indicators are taken separately, they all fall within the same level of mean ratings particularly taking on extra responsibilities, starting new tasks by themselves when the old ones were finished, taking on challenging work tasks when available, keeping up to date with the job knowledge by themselves, updating job skills by themselves, coming up with creative solutions to work-related problems, doing more than expected, actively participating in work meetings, looking for ways to improve work performance, grasping opportunities when they presented themselves and knowing how to solve difficult situations and setbacks quickly. A study suggests that contextual performance is correlated with burnout, hence, it is recommended that management need to improve contextual performance to improve employee wellness and quality of work (Palenzuela, et. Al., 2018). This holds true in higher education context. Specifically, the study by Deeba, et.al., (2021) recommended that teachers must be given the training to improve their contextual performance as teachers.

Table 7: Individual Work Performance in terms of Counterproductive behavior

Indicators	Counterproductive Behaviors	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	I complained about unimportant matters at work	2.70	SWA
2	I made problems greater than they were at work	2.56	D
3	I focused on the negative aspects of a work situation, instead of on the positive aspects	2.56	D
4	I spoke with colleagues about the negative aspects of my work	2.62	SWA
5	I spoke with people from outside the organization about the negative aspects of my work	2.56	D
6	I did less than was expected of me	2.62	SWA
7	I managed to get off from a work task easily	2.66	SWA
8	I sometimes did nothing, when I should have been working	2.61	SWA
	Composite Mean	2.61	SWA
Overall Mean	Task Performance, Contextual Performance, and Counterproductive Behavior	3.52	A

Source: Koopmans, et al (2014)

Legend:

Range of Mean Values	Descriptive Interpretation
4.21 - 5.00	Strongly agree
3.41 - 4.20	Agree
2.61 - 3.40	Somewhat agree
1.81 - 2.60	Disagree
1.00 - 1.80	Strongly disagree

Concerning the counterproductive work behavior, the data on the table displays that the individual work performance along with counterproductive work behavior got a composite mean rating of 2.61 which is understood as "disagree or low". The rating underscores that counterproductive work behavior of employees of Divine Word College of Laoag is low. It is understood that counterproductive work behaviors harm the organization and other people (Spector, et al., 2006, Spector & Fox, 2005). Minimizing counterproductive work behavior can help the organization achieve its objective. Noteworthy, these kinds of behavior result to injustices and unfair treatment that may eventually lead to stressful conditions and negative emotions (Spector & Fox, 2006).

4. Is there a relationship between organizational trust and individual work performance?

a. Organizational trust and task Performance

When cognitive trust and affective trust are taken together, they could not predict the task performance of the employees $F(2, 157) = 2.568$ $p > .05$. Hence, the variations observed in the task performance of the employees are not because of cognitive trust and affective trust, it is only by chance.

Therefore, regardless of the cognitive trust and affective trust of Divine Word Colleges, the task performance of the employees will be the same.

Table 8: Organizational Trust and Task Performance**Model Summary**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.178 ^a	.032	.019	.54706

a. Predictors: (Constant), Affective trust, cognitive trust

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	1.537	2	.768	2.568	.080 ^b
Residual	46.987	157	.299		

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
1	.097		.097	.625	.533
	.087				
	.112				
	.200		.097	.625	.533
	.058				
	.104				
	3.558		.097	.625	.533
	.070				
	.104				

a. Dependent Variable: TASK PERFORMANCE

b.

Organizational Trust and Contextual Performance

The organizational trust of Divine Word Colleges in terms of cognitive trust and affective trust when taken together could not significantly predict the contextual performance of employees, $F(2,157) = 1.934$ $p > .05$.

Thus, the differences noted in the contextual performance of the employees could not be attributed to the effects of the cognitive trust and affective trust of Divine Word Colleges. Therefore, the employees' contextual performance will be the same regardless of the changes in the cognitive trust and affective trust of Divine Word College

Table 9: Organizational Trust and Contextual Performance**Model Summary**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.155 ^a	.024	.012	.57401

a. Predictors: (Constant), AFFECTIVE TRUST, COGNITIVE TRUST

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	1.275	2	.637	1.934	.148 ^b
Residual	51.729	157	.329		
Total	53.004	159			

a. Dependent Variable: CONTEXTUAL PERFORMANCE

b. Predictors: (Constant), AFFECTIVE TRUST, COGNITIVE TRUST

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
1	.239		.239	1.529	.128
	-.109				
	.118				
	.210		.239	1.529	.128
	-.076				
	.109				
	3.613		.239	1.529	.128
	.180				
	.109				

a. Dependent Variable: CONTEXTUAL PERFORMANCE

c. Organizational Trust and Counterproductive Behavior

The Divine Word Colleges organizational trust of cognitive and affective trusts when taken together could significantly predict the counterproductive behavior of the employees, $F(2,157) = 7.012$ $p < .01$ with .286 overlap between these predictor variables and employees' counterproductive behavior.

Therefore, when cognitive trust and affective trust of Divine Word Colleges are taken together, they could predict the counterproductive behavior of the employees.

However, when cognitive trust and affective trust were taken singly, they could not predict the counterproductive behavior of the employees.

Table 10: Organizational Trust and Counterproductive behavior

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.286 ^a	.082	.070	.96899

a. Predictors: (Constant), Affective trust, cognitive trust

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	13.167	2	6.584	7.012	.001 ^b
	Residual	147.412	157	.939		
	Total	160.580	159			

a. Dependent Variable: Counterproductive work behavior

b. Predictors: (Constant), Affective trust, cognitive trust

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.371	.354		3.870	.000
	COGNITIVE TRUST	.117	.199	.089	.589	.556
	AFFECTIVE TRUST	.249	.183	.206	1.356	.177

a. Dependent Variable: Counterproductive work behavior

5. Is there a relationship between employee treatment and organizational trust?

a. Employee Treatment and Cognitive Trust

The employee treatment of worker's rights and respect in the workplace when taken together could significantly predict the cognitive trust of Divine Word Colleges, $F(2,157) = 185.488$ $p < .01$ with .838 overlap between the two predictor variables (worker's right and respect in the workplace) and cognitive trust.

Specifically, worker's right $B = .235$ $p < .01$, and respect in the workplace $B = .623$ $p < .01$, .544 quantified the Y-intercept for the regression equation.

Hence, both workers' rights and respect in the workplace could significantly predict the cognitive trust of Divine Word Colleges.

Moreover, when workers' rights and respect in the workplace were taken singly, they could still predict the cognitive trust of Divine Word Colleges.

Therefore, the differences in the worker's rights and respect in the workplace would result in variations in the cognitive trust of Divine Word Colleges.

Table 11: Employee Treatment and Cognitive Trust

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.838 ^a	.703	.699	.42068

a. Predictors: (Constant), RESPECT IN THE WORKPLACE, WORKER'S RIGHT

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	65.653	2	32.826	185.488	.000 ^b
	Residual	27.785	157	.177		
	Total	93.437	159			

a. Dependent Variable: COGNITIVE TRUST

b. Predictors: (Constant), RESPECT IN THE WORKPLACE, WORKER'S RIGHT

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.544	.155		3.513	.001
	WORKER'S RIGHT	.235	.078	.233	2.995	.003
	RESPECT IN THE WORKPLACE	.623	.076	.634	8.142	.000

b. Employee Treatment and Affective Trust

Employee treatment in terms of worker's rights and respect in the workplace when taken jointly could significantly predict the affective trust of Divine Word Colleges, $F(2,157) = 202.091$ $p < .01$ with .849 overlap between the predictor variables (worker's right and respect in the workplace) and affective trust.

Specifically, worker's right $B = .409$, $p < .01$, and respect in the workplace $B = .544$, $p < .01$, .189 quantified the Y-intercept of the regression equation.

Thus, employee treatment of workers' rights and respect in the workplace, when taken together could significantly predict the affective trust of Divine Word Colleges.

Moreover, when workers' rights and respect in the workplace were taken singly, they could also significantly predict the affective trust of Divine Word Colleges.

Therefore, the variations in the affective trust of Divine Word Colleges is due to the differences in workers' right and respect in the workplace.

Table 12: Employee Treatment and Affective trust

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.849 ^a	.720	.717	.44246

a. Predictors: (Constant), RESPECT IN THE WORKPLACE, WORKER'S RIGHT

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	79.128	2	39.564	202.091	.000 ^b
	Residual	30.736	157	.196		
	Total	109.864	159			

a. Dependent Variable: AFFECTIVE TRUST

b. Predictors: (Constant), RESPECT IN THE WORKPLACE, WORKER'S RIGHT

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.189	.163			
	WORKER'S RIGHT	.409	.082	.375		
	RESPECT IN THE WORKPLACE	.544	.080	.511		

a. Dependent Variable: AFFECTIVE TRUST

6. Is there a relationship between employee treatment and individual work performance?

a. Employee Treatment & Task Performance

Employee treatment such as workers' rights and respect in the workplace when taken together could not significantly predict the task performance of the employees, $F(2,157) = 1.422, p > .05$.

Therefore, the observed differences in the task performance of the employees are only by chance and they are not the effects of workers' rights and respect in the workplace.

Table 13: Employee treatment and Task performance

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.133 ^a	.018	.005	.55097

a. Predictors: (Constant), Respect in the workplace, workers' right

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.863	2	.432	1.422	.244 ^b
	Residual	47.660	157	.304		
	Total	48.523	159			

a. Dependent Variable: TASK PERFORMANCE

b. Predictors: (Constant), RESPECT IN THE WORKPLACE, WORKER'S RIGHT

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.685	.203		18.156	.000
	WORKER'S RIGHT	-.018	.103	-.024	-.172	.864
	RESPECT IN THE WORKPLACE	.108	.100	.153	1.079	.282

a. Dependent Variable: TASK PERFORMANCE

b. Employee Treatment & Contextual Performance

Worker's rights and respect in the workplace when taken together could not significantly predict the contextual performance of the employees, $F(2,157) = 1.403, p > .05$

Thus, regardless of the changes in workers' rights and respect in the workplace, the contextual performance of the employees will remain the same.

Table 14: Employee treatment and contextual performance

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.132 ^a	.018	.005	.57592

a. Predictors: (Constant), RESPECT IN THE WORKPLACE, WORKER'S RIGHT

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
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Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.888	.212		18.325	.000
	WORKER'S RIGHT	1.54	.107	-.204	-1.439	.152
	RESPECT IN THE WORKPLACE	.175	.105	.237	1.672	.096

b. Predictors: (Constant), RESPECT IN THE WORKPLACE, WORKER'S RIGHT

a. Dependent Variable: CONTEXTUAL PERFORMANCE

c. Employee Treatment & Counterproductive Behavior

Employee treatment in terms of worker's rights and respect in the workplace when taken together could significantly predict the employees' counterproductive behavior, $F(2,157) = 16.088, p < .01$ with .412 overlap between the predictor variables (worker's rights and respect in the workplace) and counterproductive behavior.

Specifically, worker's right $B = .709, p < .01, .997$ quantified the Y-intercept of the regression equation.

Hence, when workers' rights and respect in the workplace are taken together, they could significantly predict the counterproductive behavior of the employees. Therefore, the variations in the employees' counterproductive behavior are due to the joint effects of workers' rights and respect in the workplace.

However, when workers' rights and respect in the workplace were taken singly, it was only the worker's rights that could predict the counterproductive behavior of the employees. Therefore, any change in workers' rights would also result in a change in the counterproductive behavior of the employees.

Table 15: Employee Treatment and counterproductive behavior

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.412 ^a	.170	.160	.92132

a. Predictors: (Constant), RESPECT IN THE WORKPLACE, WORKER'S RIGHT

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	27.312	2	13.656	16.088	.000 ^b
	Residual	133.267	157	.849		
	Total	160.580	159			

a. Dependent Variable: COUNTERPRODUCTIVE BEHAVIOR

c. Predictors: (Constant), RESPECT IN THE WORKPLACE, WORKER'S RIGHT

Coefficientsa

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	.997	.339		2.939	.004
	WORKER'S RIGHT	.709	.172	.538	4.133	.000
	RESPECT IN THE WORKPLACE	-.211	.167	-.164	-1.259	.210

a. Dependent Variable: COUNTERPRODUCTIVE BEHAVIOR

Results and Discussions

The study examined the effect of organizational trust on the individual work performance of the employees, the effect of employee treatment on organizational trust, and individual work performance. The results of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) suggest that organizational trust does not affect the task and contextual performance, except counterproductive work behavior. Even if there are changes along with the cognitive and affective trust of employees toward the organization, they do not affect the task and contextual performance. It should be noted that they can affect counterproductive behavior. This suggests that organizational trust affects the counterproductive work behavior of the employees. When the employees do not trust the management, it will increase their counterproductive work behavior.

It is also the same case with the effect of employee treatment on organizational trust. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) signifies that there is a correlation between employee treatment and organizational trust. It indicates that when the employees are treated well, particularly by protecting their rights and giving them respect in the workplace, their trust in the management increases. Conversely, when they are treated badly, they lost their trust in the management. Studies have shown that when employees do not trust the managers and leaders, various forms of organizational fallouts are likely to happen specifically low engagement, high turnover, reduced innovation, willingness to go the extra mile, recommend the organization, commitment to stay with the organization, overall satisfaction and failure to achieve targeted organizational performance (Simons, 2002, Folkman, 2021, Spreitzer & Mishra, 1999). This result recommends that management needs to take heed of workers' rights and respect in the workplace to gain their trust.

In the case of the effect of employee treatment on individual work performance, the result of analysis of variance (ANOVA) demonstrates that there is no correlation between employee treatment specifically workers' rights and respect in the workplace on the task and contextual performance, except the counterproductive work behavior. The result agrees that even if there is a positive or negative change along with cognitive and affective trust on the part of the management, they do not necessarily improve or decrease the task and contextual performance. However, counterproductive work behavior affects performance. Any positive or negative change along with employee treatment such as workers' rights and respect in the workplace can affect counterproductive work behavior. A study supports this finding that unfair treatment results in counterproductive work behavior of employees (Adugna, et al, 2022).

Conclusion

The study found that organizational trust along with cognitive and affective trust is considered high. However, it is not the same case with employee treatment. The result indicates that employee treatment on both dimensions such as workers' rights and respect in the workplace is considered moderate. In the case of individual work performance, the results suggest that individual work performance in terms of task and contextual performance is high, except for counterproductive work behavior which is low.

Concerning the relationship between organizational trust and individual work performance, the analysis of variance

recommends that there is no correlation between cognitive and affective trust on task and contextual performance. Notably, organizational trust correlates with counterproductive work behavior. In the case of the effect of employee treatment on organizational trust, workers' rights and respect in the workplace correlate with organizational trust. Meanwhile, the effect of employee treatment on work performance shows the ANOVA results that there is no correlation between employee treatment and task and contextual performance. The result further points out that there is a correlation between employee treatment and counterproductive work behavior.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, D.A, F.P.J. M.G., and J. R. L.; methodology, D.A, F.P.J. M.G. J.R.L. Data Collection, M.G, J.R.L; formal analysis, D.A, F.P.J. M.G., J.R.L. writing—original draft preparation, D.A, F.P.J. writing—review and editing, D.A, F.P.J M.G., and J.R.L. All authors have read and agreed to publish the final version of the manuscript.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Ethical review and approval were waived for this study, and the research does not deal with vulnerable groups or sensitive issues.

Data Availability Statement: The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest

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